
Academic Resilience Among Senior Secondary School Students of District Rajouri in Relation to Their Self Confidence

Asma Ishtiaq

Former Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Education, BGSBU, Rajouri

ABSTRACT

Students face many challenges in their academic life. While learning, socializing and growing, students experience different emotions, friendships, relationships and physical developments as well as growth of knowledge. These day to day challenges and problems not only affect them socially, psychologically, mentally and physically but also academically. The present study was conducted to explore academic resilience among senior secondary school students of district Rajouri in relation to their self-confidence. Considering the nature of the research problem descriptive research method was adopted by the investigator. The sample for the study comprised of 396 senior secondary school students, selected through stratified random sampling from twelve senior secondary schools of district Rajouri. Academic Resilience Scale (ARS) of Mallick & Kaur, Self-confidence Scale (SCS) of Gupta & Lakhani, were administered on respondents for data collection. Statistical techniques like percentage, t- test, Pearson's coefficient of correlation were used for data analysis. All the statistical analysis was carried out through IBM SPSS (V 22) software. Results revealed Academic Resilience" and overall "Self-confidence" is shown to be strongly and positively significant.

Academic Resilience: The ability of an individual to thrive in the face of adversity is known as resilience. The Latin word "resiliens," which meaning "the pliant or elastic quality of substance," is the source of the term "academic resilience" (Joseph, 1994). Academic resilience is the ability of students to perform well academically despite facing challenging circumstances. Academic resilience is described as "the ability to effectively deal with setback, stress, or pressure in the academic setting" by Martin & Marsh (2003). Qamar and Akhtar (2019) carried out a study on elementary students to ascertain various risk factors that affect academic resilience. Lack of parental attention, adverse family background and support, lack of teacher's support, improper teaching methods, teaching style, and lack of inspiration, motivation, feedback and care of students by teachers, peer pressure, competition and personality issues, lack of effort and ability and excessive use of social media were found as risk factors affecting academic resilience. The risk factors may be personal, familial or social. The investigators recommended that teachers, students as well as parents had to play a collaborative role in combatting the odds and promoting academic resilience. Martin and Marsh (2003) propounded that there are four determinants of academic resilience - the 4 C's: 1. Confidence (Self-belief) 2. Control (a sense of control) 3. Composure (low anxiety) 4. Commitment (Persistence)

Risk factors and protective factors are two key concepts that scholars have generally examined in order to better understand academic resilience (Rutter, 1990). Research on both of these concepts may significantly advance our understanding of how students succeed in school despite adversity (Greene & Conrad, 2002). Risk variables are circumstances that may increase a student's risk of disengaging from social or academic affairs, or conditions linked to a higher likelihood of poor outcomes among students (Winfield, 1993; Murray, 2003). It is possible to refer to children who have not encountered any serious risk as competent, normal, or well-adjusted, but not resilient (Masten & Reed, 2002). Risk factors or unfavourable circumstances have a negative impact on children's ability to be resilient as well as their general development. Genetic, sociocultural, behavioural, biological, and demographic situations, traits, or features may be among these risk factors. They could be environmental, social, familial, or personal. According to Masten (1994), protective factors are those internal and external resources that mitigate the impacts of risk or adversity and promote greater competence or adaptation. According to Martin and Marsh (2006), self-efficacy, self-control, planning, low anxiety, and persistence are the five variables that predict academic resilience. Student academic resilience is significantly influenced by both external and internal protective factors, such as high expectations from both parents and peers, high expectations from school, positive self-perceptions, empathy, high educational aspirations, an internal locus of control, and hope for the future (Gizir & Aydin, 2009).

Bala and Verma (2019) conducted a study on 500 students from five different countries namely Afghanistan, Bhutan, Nepal, Nigeria and Tanzania with reference to academic resilience, education aspirations, mental health and social adjustment. Educational aspirations, mental health and social adjustment were found as significant predictors

of academic resilience. Moreover, students had a significant difference on academic resilience with reference to their gender, educational qualifications and nations. Girls were found more resilient than boys, graduate students were found more resilient than post graduate students and Nepalese were found more resilient than Afghani students.

Self-Concept : The ability to believe in oneself and one's talents is known as self-confidence. Self-confidence is a mental state characterised by one's beliefs and feelings about oneself and one's skills. Self-confidence is a mental condition that enables one to be realistic and constructive about oneself and one's situation. Self-confidence is the conviction that one can achieve the objective. The mentality of a person who believes in and relies on himself or herself and their ability to achieve the goal is known as self-confidence. One's degree of self-confidence reveals how confident they are in their own judgement. Self-confidence is a measure of one's faith, confidence, and trust in oneself and one's own talents. Riadil (2020) conducted a qualitative study on 20 students of Department of English, University of Tidar to assess the influence of self-confidence on speaking ability and language learning. Results of the study showed significant effect of self-confidence on developing speaking ability and decreasing reticence in speaking ability. Better the self-confidence, better the speaking ability. Wagh (2020) conducted a study to examine the impact of social media on selfconfidence among millennials. Structured questionnaire were administered on 65 respondents. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied for data analysis. Results of the study showed that most respondents were negatively affected by social media usage with reference to self-confidence. However, very few had positive effect on self-confidence due to social media usage. Moreover, males and females varied significantly on self-confidence and had difference of opinion about social media usage. Specifically, social media had adverse effects on self-confidence among students.

Objective

To compare the self- confidence among senior secondary school students of district Rajouri on the basis of gender.

To Study the Relationship between Academic Resilience and Self-confidence of senior secondary school students of district Rajouri.

Hypothesis

there is no significant difference in self-confidence among senior secondary school students of district Rajouri with respect to gender.

There is no significant relationship between academic resilience and self-confidence of senior secondary school students of district Rajouri.

Research Methodology The descriptive research approach was used, taking into account the nature of the study problem.

Variables Involved

Dependent Variable: Academic Resilience

Independent Variable: Self-confidence,

Demographic Variable: Gender,

Population of the Study The participants in this study were all 11th grade students from senior secondary schools in the Rajouri district that were associated with the Jammu and Kashmir State Board of School Education. The investigator chose 396 samples.

Research Tools Used The following tools were employed by the investigator for data collection for the present study:

1. Academic Resilience Scale (2015) developed by Mihir Kumarr Mallick and Simranjit Kaur.
2. Self-confidence Scale (2018) developed by Madhu Gupta and Bindiya Lakhani.

Statistical Techniques Employed The following statistical techniques were employed for the analysis of data:

- 1) t- test
- 2) Karl Pearson’s coefficient of correlation.

To determine the significance of the difference between two groups, the t-test is employed. To determine the link between the independent and dependent variables, the product moment method of correlation is applied. IBM SPSS (V.22) software was used for all statistical analyses.

INTERPERTATION

To compare the self- confidence among senior secondary school students of district Rajouri on the basis of gender.

The t-test was used to ascertain the impact of gender on the level of self-confidence among senior secondary school pupils in the Rajouri district. The t-test findings are shown in the table below, and the mean value comparison of male and female senior secondary school students is shown in the figure below to help visualise the gender effect.

Table 4.15

Mean comparison between male and female senior secondary school students of district Rajouri on self-confidence

	Group	Frequency	Mean	S.D	t-value	df	p value
Self-confidence	Male	198	196.12	20.791	1.449	398	.148
	Female	198	193.15	20.210			

Mean comparisons between male and female senior secondary school students of district Rajouri on self-confidence

It is clear from looking at the table and figure that there is no discernible difference in the level of self-confidence between male and female senior secondary school students in the Rajouri district. While their S.Ds are (20.791) and (20.210), respectively, the mean score of male senior secondary school students in the Rajouri district (196.12) is marginally higher than the mean score of female senior secondary school students in the district (193.15). Nevertheless, the p value is 0.148 and the t-value is (1.449), neither of which are statistically significant. Thus, it may be concluded that there are no appreciable differences in self-confidence between male and female senior secondary school students in the Rajouri district.

Therefore the null hypothesis stating, “*there is no significant difference in self-confidence among senior secondary school students of district Rajouri with respect to gender*” is accepted.

To Study the Relationship between Academic Resilience and Self-confidence of senior secondary school students of district Rajouri

The goal of the current study is to investigate the connection between senior secondary school pupils in the Rajouri district's academic resilience and self-confidence. Pearson's coefficient of correlation (r) was used to investigate the association between academic resilience and self-confidence in senior secondary school pupils in the Rajouri district. The provided Table displays the findings determined using Pearson's coefficient of correlation (r).

Summary of Correlation between Academic Resilience and Self-confidence among senior secondary school students of district Rajouri

	Decisiveness	Self-Concept	Self-Control	Inter-Personal Relations	Parental Support	Self-Confidence (Overall)
Academic Confidence	.703**	.694**	.705**	.566**	.477**	.718**
Sense of Well-being	.812**	.773**	.814**	.665**	.586**	.822**
and Ability to get Goals	.864**	.849**	.869**	.710**	.648**	.884**
up with Peers and Adults	.834**	.800**	.835**	.708**	.608**	.848**
Emotional Regulation and Physical Health	.860**	.827**	.866**	.682**	.638**	.871**
Academic Resilience(Overall)	.901**	.872**	.913**	.744**	.665**	.926**

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level; p < 0.01 N=40*

First, looking at the above table makes it clear that among senior secondary school students in the Rajouri district, there is a significant and positive correlation between "Academic resilience" and "self-confidence" ($r = 0.923$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that higher self-confidence is associated with greater academic resilience and vice versa. Second, the table shows that, at the 0.01 level of confidence, or (0.713**), the connection between the "Academic confidence" feature of "Academic resilience" and overall "Self-confidence" is strongly and positively significant. The same is discovered for the different aspects of "self-confidence," such as "decisiveness" (0.704**), "self-concept" (0.695**), "self-control" (0.706**), "interpersonal relations" (0.567**), and "parental support" (0.478**).

Thirdly, the table shows that, at the 0.01 level of confidence, or 0.822**, the correlation between the overall "Self-confidence" and the "Sense of well-being" dimension of "Academic resilience" is strongly and positively significant. The same is discovered for the many aspects of "self-confidence," such as "decisiveness" (0.812**), "self-concept" (0.773**), "self-control" (0.814**), "interpersonal relations" (0.665**), and "parental support" (0.586**).

Fourth, it is clear that there is a strong and positive link, at the 0.01 level of confidence, between the "Motivation and ability to get goals" facet of "Academic resilience" and general "Self-confidence," or (0.884**). The same is discovered for the many aspects of "self-confidence," such as "decisiveness" (0.864**), "self-concept" (0.849**), "self-control" (0.869**), "interpersonal relations" (0.710**), and "parental support" (0.648**).

Fifth, the table shows that, at the 0.01 level of confidence, or 0.848*, the association between the academic resilience component of "Relationship with Peers and Adults" and overall "Self-confidence" is strongly and positively significant. The same is discovered for the many aspects of "self-confidence," such as "decisiveness" (0.834**), "self-concept" (0.800**), "self-control" (0.835**), "interpersonal relations" (0.708**), and "parental support" (0.608**).

Moreover, the data shows that, at the 0.01 level of confidence, the connection between the "Emotional Regulation and Physical Health" dimension of "Academic resilience" and overall "Self-confidence" is shown to be strongly and favourably significant, or (0.871**). The same is observed for the many aspects of "self-confidence," such as "decisiveness" (0.860**), "self-concept" (0.827**), "self-control" (0.866**), "interpersonal relations" (0.682**), and "parental support" (0.638**).

Lastly, the table demonstrates that, at the 0.01 level of confidence, or 0.923**, the association between overall "Academic Resilience" and overall "Self-confidence" is shown to be strongly and positively significant. The same is discovered for the different aspects of "self-confidence," such as "decisiveness" (0.901**), "self-concept" (0.872**), "self-control" (0.913**), "interpersonal relations" (0.744**), and "parental support" (0.665**). As a result, the hypothesis that "students in senior secondary schools in the Rajouri district do not exhibit a significant relationship between academic resilience and self-confidence" is rejected.

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